

Addendum - A Passive Bistatic Range and Doppler Sensor using a Software Defined Radio with Autocorrelation Processing of ATSC Signals

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Abstract

This addendum corrects ambiguities in the original paper, and provides additional target measurement examples. Additional detail of the Doppler processing is also included.

Keywords: autocorrelation imaging, passive radar, antenna sidelobe cancellation, antenna sidelobe reduction, Doppler processing, SDR, Software Defined Radio, passive sensing.

1 overview

In the original paper [1], all measurements were made with both the reference and target antennas horizontally polarized, in agreement with the source polarization [2].

According to Lim [3], in excess of 15 dB of source cancellation is obtainable by rotating the target antenna from a co-polarized orientation to an orientation cross-polarized relative to the source (reference) orientation. For this addendum, all measurements were made using a vertically polarized target antenna, a horizontally polarized reference antenna, and the original analog vector signal canceller [1]. As in the original configuration, the canceller weight bias voltages were manually adjusted to minimize the sum of the target antenna output and the (vector rotated) reference antenna output at the receiver input. Due to the higher ratio of reference to target signal levels at the canceller input, the required weight bias settings were significantly lower than those originally required for the co-polarized antenna configuration.

2 clarification of Doppler velocity sign

The empirically measured I and Q demodulator output phase convention of the SDR [5] output data stream was shown in Figure A.2.1 [1], and was generated using a CW test signal frequency higher than the SDR band center frequency. The synthetic target generator code summarized in section 9 of [1] generates a data stream simulating the SDR output data, which is the input to the main processing code, as shown in Figure 3 [1]. To generate a simulated SDR data stream for an *approaching* or inbound target (e.g. TEST_BBBE_HC6S_04EJ.txt), the relevant portion of the generator code is:

```
'  
KAA = 33 ' number of Doppler cycles per each batch of 0 to ~ 512 * 512 = 262144  
For NZ = 0 To 402000  
NOISE  
MKA(NZ) = V9 ' random magnitude for EACH range bin  
MKB(NZ) = V9  
AKA(NZ) = 2 * pi * Rnd(1) ' random angle for EACH range bin  
Next NZ  
' PRN_gen_06_04EJ SET UP FOR APPROACHING TARGET  
B3 = 49 ' previously 27 for PRN_gen_03 ' total target signal delay  
NA% = 0  
For NZ = B3 To 402000  
If NA% >= 256 Then NA% = 0  
SHI(NZ) = MKA(NZ) * Cos(AKA(NZ))  
SHQ(NZ) = MKB(NZ) * Cos(AKA(NZ) + (pi / 2))  
SJI(NZ - B3) = MKA(NZ) * Cos(AKA(NZ) + (2 * pi * KAA * NZ / 262144))  
SJQ(NZ - B3) = MKB(NZ) * Cos(AKA(NZ) + (2 * pi * KAA * NZ / 262144) + (pi / 2))  
Next NZ  
For NZ = B3 To 401100  
FKI(NZ - B3) = Int(60 * (0.05 * SJI(NZ) + SHI(NZ)) + 0.5)  
If FKI(NZ - B3) > 128 Then FKI(NZ - B3) = 128  
If FKI(NZ - B3) < (-127) Then FKI(NZ - B3) = -127  
FKQ(NZ - B3) = Int(60 * (0.05 * SJQ(NZ) + SHQ(NZ)) + 0.5)  
If FKQ(NZ - B3) > 128 Then FKQ(NZ - B3) = 128  
If FKQ(NZ - B3) < (-127) Then FKQ(NZ - B3) = -127  
Next NZ  
'
```

To generate a simulated SDR output for a *receding* or outbound target (e.g. TEST_BBBE_HC6S_04EG.txt), everything in the previous code is unchanged except for two lines:

$$SJI(NZ - B3) = MKA(NZ) * \text{Cos}(AKA(NZ) - (2 * \pi * KAA * NZ / 262144))$$

$$SJQ(NZ - B3) = MKB(NZ) * \text{Cos}(AKA(NZ) - (2 * \pi * KAA * NZ / 262144) + (\pi / 2))$$

The target to reference amplitude ratio (0.05/.5 or -20 dB) is the same for both test cases, and is defined within two lines as:

$$FKI(NZ - B3) = \text{Int}(60 * (0.05 * SJI(NZ) + SHI(NZ))) + 0.5$$

$$FKQ(NZ - B3) = \text{Int}(60 * (0.05 * SJQ(NZ) + SHQ(NZ))) + 0.5$$

The range-Doppler analysis code will display the desired Doppler sense according to the user-specified flag 'vel. sense' value in the lower left portion of the VB user interface window.

The convention is: velocity sense 1 = outbound, velocity sense 2 = inbound.

When the *outbound* target data TEST_BBBE_HC6S_04EG.txt is analyzed by the range-Doppler code (IFFT_U_10K_4M9.vbp), the result is:

Figure AA.1

The simulated target was correctly located at Doppler = 33 cycles, range delay = 49 samples for velocity sense 1 (outbound). The target was not visible when selecting velocity sense 2.

Note that for a given batch length (NZ), only the sample delay (B3) and the Doppler cycle count (KAA) are significant. The specified sample time is only a scale factor which is used to derive absolute Doppler frequency (in Hz) and range in meters.

When the *inbound* target data TEST_BBBE_HC6S_04EJ.txt is analyzed by the range-Doppler code, the outputs are:

Figure AA.2

The simulated target was correctly located at Doppler = 33 cycles, range delay = 49 samples for velocity sense 2 (inbound). The target was not visible when selecting velocity sense 1.

The next plot is actual range-Doppler data for a helicopter at very close range, outbound during the sampling period.

Figure AA.3

batch dimensions: NTT = 512, NTU = 1024; NTT = 1024, NTU = 512
 sample rate = 1.9e6 SPS, velocity sense 1.

Figure AA.4

batch dimensions: NTT = 512, NTU = 1024; NTT = 1024, NTU = 512
sample rate = 1.9e6 SPS, no inbound targets were visible (velocity sense 2)

The target in Figure AA.3 was similar in appearance to an AS350 'Squirrel', and had a measured (round-trip) range and Doppler frequency of 972 m and 209 Hz, respectively. At 545 MHz, this corresponds to a velocity of 57.5 m/s or 111 kt.

As a cross check, the observed Doppler count was 57.7 cycles over the total observation period

$$(1/\text{sample rate}) * \text{samples} = 5.26e-7 * 512 * 1024 = 0.276 \text{ sec}$$

$$\text{Doppler frequency} = 57.7 / 0.276 = 209 \text{ Hz}$$

and the round-trip delay is

$$6.2 \text{ samples} = 6.2 * 5.263e-7 = 3.26e-6 \text{ sec}$$

$$\text{total delay, } m = 3.0e8 * 3.26e-7 = 979 \text{ m}$$

3 SDR output signal statistics

A first variant of the original range-Doppler code was created to examine only the unprocessed SDR data. Within this variant, the real and imaginary SDR data values $\text{Re}(p)$ and $\text{Im}(p)$ update the *count* of a new output series $\text{USU}(*)$ as follows:

for $n = 0$ to n_{max}

if $\text{Abs}(\text{Re}(n)) = p$ then $\text{USU}(p) = \text{USU}(p) + 1$

if $\text{Abs}(\text{Im}(n)) = p$ then $\text{USU}(p) = \text{USU}(p) + 1$

next n

where both $\text{Re}(n)$ and $\text{Im}(n)$ range from -127 to +128 (Appendix B.1)

For an SDR sample length n_{max} , $\text{USU}(*)$ is updated $2*n$ times. This new output series is the probability density function (PDF) of the unprocessed SDR output data stream $\text{UYD}(*)$.

Figure AA.5 is a PDF of actual SDR clutter data (no target).

Figure AA.5

The above is the PDF of the SDR output data file created by
`rtl_sdr -f 546300000 -s 1024000 -g 29.5 -n 400000 dJ546_3_201.txt`

For this file, $n_{max} = 400000$. Of the $(2*n_{max})$ integers evaluated, $4.087e3$ had an absolute value ≥ 127 , representing a saturation rate of $4.087e3 / 8.0e5 \approx 0.51\%$.

The parameters of the empirically generated normal distribution in Figure AA.5 are

$$\alpha = 48$$

$$K2 = 1.325E4$$

$$\text{counts} / n = K2 * \exp(-n^2 / (2 * (\alpha^2)))$$

Another variant of the range-Doppler code illustrates the Rayleigh probability density function of the range-Doppler processed output data. Within the new code the magnitude of each range-Doppler output element updates the count of the corresponding PDF matrix element USU(*) as follows:

```
for nz = 0 to (NTT - 1)
  for rrc = 0 to (NTU - 1)
    UYD(rrc, nz) = Sqr((Re(rrc)) ^ 2 + (Im(rrc)) ^ 2)
    USU(Int(UYD(rrc, nz))) = USU(Int(UYD(rrc, nz))) + 1
  next rrc
next nz
```


Figure AA.6

The above is the PDF of the range-Doppler output for SDR data file
rtl_sdr -f 546300000 -s 1024000 -g 29.5 -n 400000 dJ546_3_201.txt

For the data input file, $n_{max} = 400000$, of which only $262144 = (512*512)$ were used. The process output generated $259081 = ((511*511) - 2040)$ values as plotted in Figure AA.6. The parameters of the Rayleigh distribution in Figure AA.6 are

$$\sigma = 12.70$$

$$K2 = 2.59e5$$

$$counts / n = K2 * (n / (\sigma^2)) * \exp(-n^2 / (2 * (\sigma^2)))$$

Figure AA.7
The PDF of the IFFT_U_10K_4M9.vbp range-Doppler output, for SDR data file

```
rtl_sdr -f 546300000 -s 1024000 -g 39 -n 550000 dJ546_3_333.txt
```

For the data input file, $n_{max} = 550000$, of which only $524288 = (512*1024)$ were used. The process output generated $519689 = ((511*1023) - 3064)$ values as plotted in Figure AA.7. Of these, 28 values had an absolute value ≥ 127 , representing a saturation rate of $28 / 519689 \approx 0.0054\%$. The parameters of the Rayleigh distribution in Figure AA.7 are

$$\sigma = 27.875$$

$$K2 = 5.197e5$$

$$counts / n = K2 * (n / (\sigma^2)) * \exp(-n^2 / (2 * (\sigma^2)))$$

4 sampling transfer function

According to [6], [7], an SDR using the RTL2832U has a 2.4 MSPS sampling rate limit. To characterize the SDR performance at lower sample rates, a commercial broadband modular amplifier was used as a noise source. For this device, $G_p \geq 28$ dB, $NF \approx 5$ dB, bandwidth $\approx 5 - 1500$ MHz, and $Z_{in} = Z_{out} = 50$ ohm. The amplifier input was terminated in a 50 ohm load, and a matched 3 dB attenuator was inserted between the amplifier output and the SDR input.

With the gain held constant at 44.5 dB the SDR sampling rate was stepped over $1.0 \text{ MSPS} \leq SR \leq 2.4 \text{ MSPS}$, with additional sample rates of 1.024 MSPS and 2.048 MSPS. The SDR RMS output values $\text{Sqr}(\text{Re}(n)^2 + \text{Im}(n)^2)$ are plotted in Figure AA.8 below.

Figure AA.8

* the actual SDR sample rate did not always agree with the command-line specified sample rate, as summarized below. The text in the 'actual rate' column is included in the terminal response returned by the gqrx software [4] after commands were executed.

commanded rate	actual rate
1.0 MSPS	Exact sample rate is: 1000000.026491 Hz
1.024 MSPS	Sampling at 1024000 S/s.
1.2 MSPS	Sampling at 1200000 S/s.
1.4 MSPS	Exact sample rate is: 1400000.018544 Hz
1.5 MSPS	Exact sample rate is: 1500000.014901 Hz

1.6 MSPS	Sampling at 1600000 S/s.
1.8 MSPS	Sampling at 1800000 S/s.
2.0 MSPS	Exact sample rate is: 2000000.052982 Hz
2.048 MSPS	Sampling at 2048000 S/s.
2.1 MSPS	Exact sample rate is: 2100000.125170 Hz
2.2 MSPS	Exact sample rate is: 2200000.014570 Hz
2.3 MSPS	Exact sample rate is: 2300000.022848 Hz
2.4 MSPS	Sampling at 2400000 S/s.

The SDR predetection noise bandwidth is claimed to be internally adjusted to be proportional to the sample rate. As the noise source is very wideband, the total noise power in the predetection bandwidth should be directly proportional to the sample rate. Between the sample rates $SR = 1.024$ to 2.048 MS/s, the RMS output levels were close to the expected values:

$$V_{out_{SR}} = V_{out_{1.024}} * Sqr(SR / 1.024)$$

$$Sqr(V_{out_{2.048}} / V_{out_{1.024}}) \approx Sqr(30.5 / 21.5) \approx 1.414...$$

Except for a small overall gain difference, the output level versus sample rate behavior in Figure AA.8 was duplicated using a second SDR of the same type and date. No SDR interface software other than gqrx was used for all measurements.

5 errata

The original interconnection diagram (Figure A.3.1) was ambiguous. The 75:50 ohm impedance transformer and a 75:50 matching attenuator are incorrectly shown connected in cascade in the target antenna path. All reported measurements in the original paper and this addendum used only the impedance transformer XF2. The 75:50 matching attenuator was utilized (and without the impedance transformer) only for initially verifying antenna gain flatness across the operating band. The correct configuration for data collection is:

Figure AA.9

Appendix B.1

By default, the gqrx software saved all SDR output data in binary format, e.g. dj546_3_3_60.dat .

To make this data interoperable with other software, the binary values were offset by (-127) and saved as text, using additional VB code:

```
Open "c:\users\usertwo\dj546_3_3_60.dat" For Binary Access Read As #1
For J = 0 To 1100000
    Get #1, , SH(J)
Next J
Close #1
.
Open "c:\users\usertwo\dj546_3_3_60.txt" For Output As #1
Do While J < 1100000
    SAK1 = Val(SH(J)) - 127
    SAK2 = Val(SH(J + 1)) - 127
    J = J + 2
    Write #1, K2, SAK1, SAK2
    K2 = K2 + 1
Loop
Close #1
```

where SAK1 and SAK2 are the $\text{Re}(n)$ and $\text{Im}(n)$ components, respectively, of each SDR sample pair. The final step saves the converted data as text, where both SAK1 and SAK2 range from -127 to +128 , e.g. as SAK1 or SAK2 = (the two's complement value) + 1

Appendix B.2

To ensure that the internal A/D converters of the SDR did not exhibit foldback or other non-monotonic behavior, the SDR was intentionally overdriven with a 539.000 MHz CW test signal, and Re and Im data values were recorded using

```
rtl_sdr -f 538950000 -s 1024000 -g 27 -n 50000 dL538_95_001.dat
```

thus the input to the SDR A/D converters was $539.0 - 538.95 = 50$ KHz. A short segment of the resulting $\text{Re}(\ast)$ and $\text{Im}(\ast)$ SDR output data is plotted in Figure AA.10 .

Figure AA.10

The steps in the plotted waveforms were due to inadequate filtering of PLL correction pulses within the 539 MHz source.

Bibliography

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